

Underdiagnosis of Endometriosis and Delays to Surgical Intervention: A Review of Current Challenges and Clinical Implications

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Introduction

Endometriosis is a chronic inflammatory gynaecological condition that affects approximately 10% of women of reproductive age. Despite its high prevalence, it remains underdiagnosed in surgical practice, as definitive diagnosis requires laparoscopic confirmation, making it both a gynaecological and surgical concern. Symptom overlap with conditions such as adenomyosis contributes to misdiagnosis, and diagnostic delays pose a challenge for physicians. This review highlights key factors contributing to delays in diagnosis and treatment.

Materials and methods

A narrative literature review was conducted using PubMed (2020–2025). Keywords included "endometriosis," "diagnostic delay," and "surgical management." Peer-reviewed studies (original research and reviews) focusing on time to diagnosis, barriers to care and surgical outcomes were prioritised. Twenty-one studies were included in the review.

Results

Across the reviewed literature, the average time from symptom onset to confirmed diagnosis consistently ranged from 7 to 10 years. Contributing factors to the delay include normalisation of pelvic pain, misdiagnosis, and a preference for empirical hormonal therapy over early laparoscopy, despite the inconsistent response to treatment. This results in physician-driven delays that complicate surgical management. Disease progression, particularly in the posterior pelvis, may lead to dense fibrosis and severe adhesions, increasing surgical complexity and sometimes requiring ureterolysis, bowel resection, or bladder cystectomy, with elevated costs, complications and risks to fertility. Therefore, earlier intervention may prevent progression to a technically demanding condition with compromised reproductive prognosis. Some studies suggest that gender-related biases in the interpretation of women's symptoms may contribute to delays in referral, with some reports indicating that symptoms are sometimes minimised or may require external validation before referral.

Conclusion

Delayed diagnosis and surgical intervention in endometriosis stem from systemic delays, variability in disease presentation, and its chronic non-urgent perception. A multifaceted response is therefore required, including streamlining referral pathways, reducing barriers to early diagnosis, and ensuring timely laparoscopic assessment to improve patient outcomes.

Keywords

Endometriosis, Delayed diagnosis, Laparoscopy, Fibrosis, Pelvic pain